

CHARACTERISTICS OF TRANSLATION WITHIN THE FRAMEWORK OF TOURIST DISCOURSE

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Abstract. *The current period of social development is characterized by a much greater mobility of people, as well as an increased demand for tourist services. Due to the rapid development of the international tourism industry, it has become necessary to consider important issues of translation studies within the framework of tourism discourse. The websites of travel companies are developing, gaining their English language versions. The proper translation of the text of such sites with the description of the offered tourist services into English becomes the key to their effective sale to a foreign tourist.*

Keywords: *translation, discourse, tourist discourse, text, speech, cognitive processes.*

Аннотация. *Современный период развития общества характеризуется значительно большей мобильностью людей, а также повышенным спросом на туристические услуги. В связи с бурным развитием индустрии международного туризма возникла необходимость рассмотрения важных вопросов переводоведения в рамках туристического дискурса. Сайты туристических компаний развиваются, обрастая англоязычными версиями. Правильный перевод текста таких сайтов с описанием предлагаемых туристических услуг на английский язык становится залогом их эффективной продажи иностранному туристу.*

Ключевые слова: *перевод, дискурс, туристический дискурс, текст, речь, когнитивные процессы.*

Annotatsiya. *Jamiyat rivojlanishining zamonaviy davri odamlarning sezilarli darajada harakatchanligi, shuningdek, turizm xizmatlariga talabning ortishi bilan tavsiflanadi. Xalqaro turizm industriyasining jadal rivojlanishi munosabati bilan tarjimashunoslikning muhim masalalarini turizm nutqi doirasida ko‘rib chiqish zarurati paydo bo‘ldi. Sayyohlik kompaniyalarining saytlari ingliz tilidagi versiyalari bilan o‘sib bormoqda. Taklif etilayotgan turistik xizmatlarning tavsifi bilan bunday saytlarning matnini ingliz tiliga to‘g‘ri tarjima qilish ularni chet ellik sayyohga samarali sotishning kalitiga aylanadi.*

Kalit so‘zlar: *tarjima, nutq, turistik nutq, matn, nutq, kognitiv jarayonlar.*

While studying the features of such a phenomenon as tourist discourse, first of all, it is necessary to turn to its basis - the term of discourse itself. What is discourse? Commonly available sources show us that the origin of this word refers to several languages at once. Thus, in Greek the word discourse means a path, an argument or a story, in Latin it means a conversation, an opinion, an argument or a talk, and in French it means a speech.

According to N. D. Arutyunova, discourse is “a cohesive text in conjunction with extralinguistic - pragmatic, sociocultural, psychological and other factors; text taken in the event aspect; speech considered as a purposeful social action, as a component involved in the interaction of people and mechanisms of their consciousness (cognitive processes)” [1, p. 136-137]. The given definition, discourse is a coherent text in the totality of extralinguistic - extra-linguistic - and

pragmatic, socio-cultural, psychological and other factors. A coherent text always conveys the thoughts of the person writing it in a certain form inherent to this person. The structure and content of a coherent text carry extralinguistic components that are related to its author, his social, cultural, psychological and other attitudes and factors affecting his life. It is also true to consider discourse as speech in the context of purposeful social action, and as a component involved in the interaction of people and the mechanisms of their consciousness.

The speech is obviously a component of human interaction, a way for people to communicate with each other, as well as a component of mental (cognitive) processes such as attention, memory, and perception. Both perception and memory are fundamental cognitive processes of any individual. Content of speech and the form of presenting information that is acceptable or unacceptable to the audience allows the reader to accept the author's position, agree with it and memorize the information offered or, on the contrary, close the book, turn the page being studied.

Considering and studying this definition, it is possible to offer our own definition of discourse as a multidimensional term of text linguistics, a way of speech interaction based on the presentation of the text using the author's inherent socio-cultural, psychological and other features of speech, aimed at the attention of specific individuals, social group or an indeterminate circle of persons (target audience). Our proposed definition of discourse allows us to talk about the mandatory social orientation of discourse as an important element of speech interaction, which allows us to start researching the application of discourse in tourism. In order to successfully compose texts whose purpose is to promote tourist services, it becomes necessary to study and systematize the characteristic features inherent in the texts of tourist discourse. Learning specific discursive principles is also important for translators, because with their help he is able to develop basic translation strategies.

The authors' typology of key principles of English-language tourist discourse under the authorship of A. O. Tsyrepilon, candidate of philological sciences, and T. Platitsyna, candidate of cultural studies, was chosen as the main characteristic [5, p. 123-131]. The following were emphasized among the main characteristics in this typology: 1) inducement; 2) expressiveness; 3) personalization; 4) accessibility; 5) informativeness [4, p. 4]. The material for the study of texts of tourist discourse in this article were texts in Russian, as well as their translation into English, taken from the website of the popular travel company Russia Discovery, offering travels in Russia [5; 2; 3]. Motivation as a characteristic feature of tourist discourse texts is justified by the fact that, according to many researchers, tourist discourse is perceived as a subspecies of advertising discourse, the purpose of which is to promote and sell tourist services. English-language texts of tourist discourse are characterized by exclamations expressing an inducement to action: “ Check out what's new in Chicago - Find out what's new in Chicago! “ [4, c. 3].

The use of the imperative verbs (find, cross, explore) instead of the infinitive verbs of the original in the English-language advertising text makes the English version more motivational. The last phrase (Become one of travelers who have reached the North Pole) is translated verbatim, preserving the inducement inherent in the original. The expressiveness is achieved through the use of various stylistic means provoking the emergence of vivid images and associations in the minds of the audience. Due to the already mentioned close connection with advertising discourse, the texts of tourist discourse are characterized by a set of typical techniques that are usually used by advertisers.

First of all, the translator should stylistically analyze the text, paying attention to the variety of stylistic devices used. The above-mentioned inducement is to some extent also a device of expressiveness characteristic of such texts. Expressiveness of texts of tourist discourse is mainly achieved by epithets, metaphors and hyperboles.

The English-language version contains a rather expressive greeting “*Welcome to the geographic North Pole!*”, emphasizing the significance and exclusivity of the event, while the original has only an introductory participle, setting the stage for the upcoming description of the route. The significance of the moment in the English version is also emphasized by the epithet expressed by an adverb in the phrase “*...we ceremoniously drop the anchor on a sturdy stretch of ice*”..., which is absent in the original.

Personalization is also an integral characteristic of texts of tourist discourse, because it allows to get closer to the reader, to address him directly, thanks to which the recipient of the text can create a “presence effect”, as if he is already mentally going on a trip and talking to the guide. Personalization is achieved mainly through the use of personal addresses: YOU. Let's look at an example: *По пути вы сможете любоваться живописными пейзажами бескрайней красотой, заснеженных гор и побережья. - Along the way you can admire the picturesque landscapes of endless beauty, snow-covered mountains and the coast.*

It is obvious that when translating into English, the text gained a little more personification. The mention of a certain “exotic tradition” of building stone pyramids “for good luck” and a detailed description of the local flora and fauna, which are absent in the original, are also intended to interest the foreign tourist. This translation preserves and enhances the expressiveness of the original through the use of epithets, metaphor and hyperbole (emphasized in the English-language text), and creates the effect of the reader's presence on the excursion. The next criterion of tourist discourse texts is accessibility. The target audience of a tourist discourse text is usually people who want to have a rest, relax and get new impressions. The majority of tourists are not ready to read complex texts full of “dry” facts. The text should be written for a wide audience in modern language and translated according to the same principles. In addition, the principle of accessibility can be interpreted as the need for pragmatic adaptation of the text for a foreign reader, because such texts are often full of realities that are incomprehensible to foreign-speaking audiences. You will experience the feelings of the heroes of the legendary story “Samarkanda”, or “Timur’s Gadens”.....This case illustrates interesting translation transformations, namely, translation adaptation.

The final key criterion of tourist discourse texts is informativeness. The texts describing tourist services are informative, coherent and logical. A text's informativeness consists in the fact that it should contain all the information necessary for tourists about the planned trip. The complexity of compliance with this principle is that, along with the presence of important details of the excursion and cultural (historical) facts, the text should not be overloaded with them. The reader should familiarize himself with all the important information, but should not get bored. That is why the writer of the text, as well as its translator, is faced with the question of whether it is necessary to include or omit this or that information. Moreover, the translator must be familiar with the different measurement systems and be prepared to translate precision information from one system to another. Knowledge of abbreviations commonly used in tourism and their equivalents is also necessary. Let us refer to the example : В 8:00 состоится общий сбор группы на площади Регистан и возможны задержки из-за утреннего тумана в городе. В 9:00 вы получите метеосводку. -At 8:00 there will be a general gathering of the group at the Registan

square and there may be delays due to morning fog in the city.....The translation preserved all the precision information and conveyed it without distortion. For specific words and phrases like “weather report” and “Registan square”, according to the English corpus, the appropriate equivalents “weather report” and “Registan” have been selected. Nevertheless, when translating the toponym Registan , a mistake was made, because the generally accepted translation is “Registan square”, which the translator should have familiarized himself with beforehand. The examples were used to analyze the main characteristics and principles of construction of tourist texts where the following were emphasized: 1) encouragement; 2) accessibility; 3) personalization; 4) informativeness; 5) expressiveness.

To conclude, we consider it necessary to note that for successful and correct translation of texts of tourist discourse the translator needs to: 1) competently determine the purpose of translation and the recipient of the text; 2) familiarize himself with all the specific vocabulary, find suitable equivalents, if any; 3) preserve the original expressiveness of the text, its advertising component; 4) if necessary, adapt the text for a foreign reader.

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